

SOCIAL SCIENCES

EVALUATION OF INNOVATION FROM A STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT PERSPECTIVE AND SMES

Cagiran Kendirli H.

Asist. Prof. Dr.

Hitit University, FEAS, Department of Management, Türkiye

Arli S.

Hitit University, FEAS, Department of Management, Türkiye

ABSTRACT

The high level of innovation resulting from globalization places companies in an extremely competitive environment. Only those companies that make the most of information technology and differentiate themselves from their competitors through differentiated products and services can survive. To thrive, they must constantly innovate and adapt to changing conditions. Strategic management decisions are crucial to these innovations and changes. One such decision is innovation itself. Although innovation and strategic management are fundamentally different concepts, they are closely related. In today's dynamic world, companies need strategic management awareness and the effective implementation of innovation processes to survive and grow in highly competitive markets. In today's globalized world, many companies are forced to renew their internal structures due to changing market demands, increasing competition, shorter product life cycles, and technological advances. This study examines the relationship between strategic management and innovation in light of key conceptual frameworks and insights from the literature.

Keywords: Management, Strategic Management, Innovation, Innovation in Management, SMEs.

1. INTRODUCTION

The accelerated global change since the Industrial Revolution, particularly in the Information Age, has created a structure in which technological developments affect virtually all sectors simultaneously, and information and communication technologies have become the dominant force. This rapid change transforms organizational and social structures into constantly evolving dynamic systems and compels companies to closely monitor economic, political, social, and technological changes in their internal and external environments (Kılıç, 2023: 70). At the same time, the development of communication and transportation infrastructure, the shift in marketing understanding, globalization, and increasing international competition have intensified competitive pressure among companies, necessitating the adoption of more innovative approaches and practices to secure a competitive edge (Hancıoğlu & Yeşilaydın, 2016: 106–107).

In this context, strategy and strategic management constitute the fundamental management framework that companies rely on to survive in an uncertain and highly competitive environment. In management literature, strategy is understood as the entirety of paths and methods that companies pursue to achieve their objectives in highly competitive markets. Over time, these paths and methods have paved the way for the emergence of an independent discipline: strategic planning and its further development, strategic management (Aktan, 2008: 6). The success of strategic management activities depends on the company's ability to identify and implement strategies that give it a competitive advantage; in other words, on its ability to establish a lasting balance between changing environmental conditions and its internal resources and capabilities (Aslan, 2019: 9).

Innovation, on the other hand, has become a crucial factor for the competitiveness of countries, industries, and companies in modern economies. Innovation is considered key to economic growth, increased employment, and a higher quality of life, and is essential for companies in virtually all sectors at the product, service, and process levels (Satı & Işık, 2011: 538; Hancıoğlu & Yeşilaydın, 2016: 106–107). While Schumpeter understands innovation as a process that encompasses new technologies and new business models and provides competitive advantages, Rogers (1995) defines innovation as an idea, practice, or object that is perceived as new by individuals. Damanpour interprets innovation as the process of adapting, developing, and creating new ideas that influence a company's success; Trott, on the other hand, views innovation within the framework of managing all activities related to idea generation, technology development, the design of new or improved products, processes, and facilities, as well as the marketing process (Damanpour, 1991; Trott, 1998).

At this point, it becomes clear that innovation efforts have evolved from incidental or purely technical applications left to the research and development department to a strategic management area encompassing the entire organization. Innovation management means that the company holistically organizes its technology, business processes (customers, suppliers, financial and external resources, etc.), as well as its culture, communication, and organizational structure with regard to the human factor, in such a way as to support and promote innovation (Kalay et al., 2015: 68). In this context, the success of innovations depends not only on the available human resources, technologies, information, and equipment, but also on the organization's ability to manage these resources from a strategic perspective (Kalay et al., 2015: 67–68).

The relationship between strategic management and innovation is not simply a juxtaposition of two separate areas. In today's economic environment, organizations must create a certain synergy between strategy and innovation to generate differentiated added value (Satı & Işık, 2011: 539). The concept of strategic innovation expresses precisely this synergy. It refers to the integration of a company's strategic direction with innovative activities and leads to fundamental changes in the business model, value proposition, and market positioning that extend beyond existing products and processes (Hancıoğlu & Yeşilaydın, 2016: 105–106; Satı & Işık, 2011: 539–540). As Kılıç (2023: 70) emphasizes, strategic innovation provides a framework that integrates all types of innovation, thus enabling sustainability, long-term profitability, competitive advantages, and diversification. It also prompts the company to consider the entire system in addition to the product and process. SMEs are an important aspect of this strategic perspective.

Although small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) make a crucial contribution to the economy in terms of employment, value creation, and entrepreneurship, they are particularly exposed to intense competitive pressure, resource scarcity, and uncertainty. Çetinkaya and Gülbahar (2019: 349–350) note that strategic management awareness and the successful implementation of innovation processes have become essential for both the survival and growth of SMEs. However, few studies examine the synergy between strategic management and innovation in SMEs. This underscores the need for theoretical and applied research that addresses the relationship between strategic management and innovation, especially from the perspective of strategic innovation (Çetinkaya & Gülbahar, 2019: 350; Kalay et al., 2015: 67).

[Note: The last sentence about strategic management and innovation is unrelated and appears to be a separate, unrelated statement. It has been omitted from the translation.] The aim of this article is to examine the relationship between strategic management and innovation in light of prominent conceptual frameworks and findings from the literature and to discuss, from a theoretical perspective, organizations' efforts to achieve sustainable competitive advantages, particularly through the concept of strategic innovation. The study first addresses the concepts of strategic management and innovation. It then examines the dimensions of strategic innovation, its position within the strategic management process, and its relationship to organizational performance. The final section presents discussions and recommendations based on findings from the literature, offering assessments of how strategic management and innovation can be addressed in organizations through an integrated approach.

2. Theoretical Foundations of Strategic Management and Innovation

2.1. The Concept of Strategy and Strategic Management

In an increasingly competitive environment, companies achieve their goals not by chance, but through deliberate decisions and a long-term perspective. In this context, strategy is understood as a set of orientations and decisions that demonstrate how defined goals can be achieved with maximum performance and limited resources (Aslan, 2019: 10).

Strategy determines the areas in which the company will operate, the competencies it will emphasize, and the methods and approaches that will differentiate it from its competitors, taking into account the opportunities and threats of its environment.

Strategic management, on the other hand, is a dynamic process that encompasses the planning, implementation, and continuous review of this strategic direction. As a combination of management and strategy concepts, strategic management is a comprehensive management approach that includes setting goals in line with the company's mission and vision, analyzing external conditions and internal capacities, developing suitable strategic alternatives, and implementing them throughout the organization (Çetinkaya and Gülbahar, 2019: 350).

Strategy In this context, strategic management is understood not only as a planning activity but also as a continuous decision-making process in which implementation, monitoring, and learning are mutually dependent.

In competitive economic systems, strategy is a fundamental management tool that enables companies to adapt to environmental changes and even actively manage them. The success of a strategy depends on the quality of the company's reciprocal adaptation to its environment, the extent of its ability to develop innovative approaches to achieve this adaptation, and the extent of its ability to control change (Satı and Işık, 2011: 539–540).

Therefore, strategic management requires companies to prepare not only for their current situation but also for possible future scenarios; it focuses on flexibility, learning capacity, and innovation under uncertainty (Aktan, 2008: 6).

In today's understanding, strategic management is no longer simply about creating long-term plans in the classical sense. In an environment of increasing uncertainty, accelerated technological change, and frequently shifting customer expectations, strategic management offers a holistic framework. This framework aligns the company's vision with stakeholder interests, develops competencies that secure competitive advantages, and supports these competencies through innovative practices. From this perspective, strategic management has evolved into one of the fundamental management philosophies that activates a company's innovation potential and enables sustainable competitive advantages (Aslan, 2019: 10–12; Çetinkaya and Gülbahar, 2019: 350).

2.2. The Concept and Types of Innovation

In economic literature, innovation is not understood merely as a narrowly defined technical activity in the sense of "novelty," but rather as the process of implementing a new or significantly improved product, process, marketing method, or organizational practice that generates economic and social value (OECD, 2005).

In this sense, innovation is a dynamic process that encompasses both the outcome of a new product or application and the phases of creative thinking, development, and commercialization that lead to this outcome (Morris, 2013: 6). According to Drucker, innovation is a function that constitutes the essence of entrepreneurship; it is the fundamental tool that reveals the ability to create wealth in situations such as the creation of a new business, the transformation of public institutions, or the establishment of a new enterprise by an individual (Drucker, 1985: 5–6).

In this sense, innovation is a function that constitutes the essence of entrepreneurship. In the definitions cited by Tankişi, innovation is also emphasized as the creation of something new, the significant differentiation of an existing product or process, and the transformation of this novelty into a marketable value proposition (Tankişi, 2019: 57–58).

Commonly, innovation is understood as the successful implementation of new ideas into economic or social value; therefore, innovation cannot be reduced solely to the field of science and technology, but only gains significance through value creation (Tankişi, 2019: 57–58).

For companies, innovation is an important competitive tool that reduces costs, increases efficiency and profitability, and enables entry into new markets as well as expansion into existing ones (Özgür Güler and Kanber, 2011: 62).

The European Commission's Green Paper on Innovation emphasizes that innovation is a driving force for achieving long-term corporate goals, enables the emergence of new industries, contributes to the renewal of industrial structures, and forms the core of entrepreneurial spirit. The same text emphasizes that innovation is not only a technical process but also a transformative instrument expected to provide solutions to numerous societal problems—from healthcare to environmental protection (European Commission, 1995).

The degree of innovation depends on the impact of the changes it brings about on the market and the environment. Therefore, innovation is always market-oriented for companies; for innovations to be considered as such within an organization, they depend on their ability to generate commercial revenue and competitiveness (Drucker, 1985: 30–31).

The ability of companies to adapt to changing technological conditions and customer expectations, and to transform environmental changes from a threat into an opportunity, depends significantly on their openness to innovation activities (Uzkurt, 2010). The types of innovation are classified in the literature according to various criteria. According to the widely accepted OECD classification, innovation is divided into

four main categories: product innovation, process innovation, marketing innovation, and organizational innovation (Çetinkaya and Gülbahar, 2019: 353).

Product innovation refers to the development of new products whose technical specifications, content, materials, software, or functional characteristics differ significantly. The goal is to reduce costs and gain a competitive advantage while simultaneously increasing product performance and variety (Çetinkaya and Gülbahar, 2019: 353–354). Process innovation encompasses fundamental changes to a company's production or service processes using new technologies, equipment, and software to increase efficiency and reduce unit costs (Aktaş, 2018).

Marketing innovation focuses on better meeting customer needs, opening up new markets, or repositioning products through the use of previously unused methods in design, packaging, positioning, advertising, or pricing. Organizational innovation, on the other hand, is the application of a new organizational method in the business practices, workplace organization, or external relations of the company; it includes innovative arrangements in areas such as division of labor, distribution of authority and responsibility, and integration of different activities (Çetinkaya and Gülbahar, 2019: 353–354).

Other classifications also group innovation according to its application area, impact, and scope of change. For example, according to the classification adapted by Tankişi, Ünal, and Kılınç from Sattler, types of innovation are considered along three dimensions: product and process innovations with regard to application; social and organizational innovations with regard to scope; and radical and incremental innovations with regard to the degree of change (Sattler, 2011: 10–11; Ünal and Kılınç, 2016: 102).

Innovation is thus conceptualized as a comprehensive field of transformation that is not merely a technical innovation but extends from the organization's products to its processes, from its marketing activities to its organizational structure.

2.3. The Concept of Strategic Innovation

In today's environment of intensified global competition and blurred market boundaries, traditional competitive strategies are often no longer sufficient for companies. As the study by Hancıoğlu and Yeşilaydın shows, the rapid development of communication and information technologies, changing customer structures, and globalization are forcing companies to rethink their existing strategic structures and marketing approaches. Innovation is at the heart of this new competitive paradigm (Hancıoğlu and Yeşilaydın, 2016: 106–108).

Strategic innovation is a competitive approach driven by the synergy between corporate strategies and a company's innovative capacity. The goal is to create new value for customers, surprise competitors, expand the market, and tap into new markets (Hamel, 1998: 8).

Schlegelmilch et al. Strategic innovation is defined as the reconceptualization of business models and the transformation of existing markets in response to changing competitive rules (Schlegelmilch et al., 2003: 117–118). A common denominator of these definitions

is that strategic innovation focuses on fundamental changes to the business model, the value creation logic, and the market structure, rather than on product innovations.

While Govindarajan and Trimble view strategic innovation as a form of innovation that requires abandoning existing practices in value chain design, conceptualizing customer value, and identifying potential customers, Drejer assesses strategic innovation as a new business concept that necessitates a rethinking of the entire company, including its business systems, core competencies, and market structure (Govindarajan and Trimble, 2004: 69; Drejer, 2006: 145).

Abraham and Knight, on the other hand, interpret strategic innovation as an effort to expand the market, create new markets, and restructure the entire business strategy, rather than simply reacting to customer demand (Abraham and Knight, 2001: 22). Based on these approaches, three main outcomes of strategic innovation can be derived: the development of new business models, the emergence of new markets or the transformation of existing markets, and the creation of added value for customers and companies (Hancıoğlu and Yeşilaydın, 2016: 109–196).

Markides' study, which examined successful companies from various industries, also shows that strategic innovation is at the heart of the sustainable success of companies such as Unilever, Canon, Texas Instruments, Apple, Starbucks, and Yamaha (Markides, 1997: 9–10).

Markides' study, which examined successful companies from various industries, also shows that strategic innovation is at the core of the sustainable success of companies like Unilever, Canon, Texas Instruments, Apple, Starbucks, and Yamaha (Markides, 1997: 9–10).

When considering the components of strategic innovation, it is emphasized that top-level leaders must master strategic thinking for the present and future, strike a balance between innovation and effectiveness, and be able to conduct creative idea generation and analytical evaluation in parallel (Drejer, 2006: 144–145).

In the study by Schlegelmilch et al., based on the MIMIC model, four fundamental factors for the development of strategic innovation are identified: culture, processes, people, and resources. The components of strategic innovation are summarized under the terms customer value and competitive positioning (Schlegelmilch et al., 2003: 119–127).

In summary, strategic innovation represents an approach that redefines the relationship between corporate strategy and innovative capacity. Competitive advantage is based not only on improvements to existing products and processes, but also on a fundamental questioning of the business model and market structure. Strategic management and innovation should therefore not be viewed as two separate areas, but as two complementary dimensions that determine the long-term success of the company, influence each other and must be considered together (Satı and Işık, 2011: 540–542; Hancıoğlu and Yeşilaydın, 2016: 106–110).

3. Synergy Between Strategic Management and Innovation: Strategic Innovation Approaches

3.1. Synergy Between Strategic Management and Innovation

Strategic management and innovation, whose conceptual framework was outlined in the first chapter, are not viewed as two separate areas that develop independently in practice, but rather as different facets of the same whole. Strategic management is a process that aims to determine the long-term direction of the organization by systematically evaluating the strong and weak signals from the internal and external environment and developing corresponding goals and strategies. This process involves not only making decisions about the future of the organization, but also deciding how resources are allocated and in which areas they are concentrated (Bircan, 2003; Diken, Öge & Aslan, 2006).

Innovation management, on the other hand, is a more specialized management field that considers technological developments, changes in production processes, and the organization's internal and external relationships together, and guides the emergence and institutionalization of innovations. Satı (2010) describes innovation management as an integrated management process that combines a company's resources—knowledge, technology, human capital, and financial strength—to create innovations. This process encompasses planning, implementation, monitoring, and results evaluation (Satı & Işık, 2011: 543).

This definition clarifies that strategic management and innovation management represent two fundamental management functions that complement each other and operate on the same foundation. According to Satı and Işık (2011: 540), increasing competitive pressure, accelerated technological change, and the volatility of market dynamics are forcing companies to move beyond the traditional understanding of innovation. Innovation has become an indispensable tool for organizations to gain a competitive edge and respond flexibly and proactively to customer needs. Therefore, innovation decisions should not be left to chance. They should be addressed within the framework of an innovation strategy that aligns with the company's overall strategy. In other words, there is a strong interdependence between fundamental corporate strategies and innovation strategies.

In the context of innovation, the fundamental corporate strategies and innovation strategies are highly interdependent. The authors emphasize that in competitive economic environments, strategy is essentially a management tool designed to ensure innovation, progress, and the company's adaptation to its environment. For effective innovation management, the concepts of "strategic action" and "leadership" are crucial success factors; companies without a solid strategic framework cannot consistently and holistically implement the necessary steps of the innovation process (Cormican & O'Sullivan, 2004).

This emphasis underscores the need to establish an organic link between strategic management and innovation management. At this point, the concept of strategic innovation emerges as an overarching term that

expresses the intersection of innovation logic and corporate strategies. Hancıoğlu and Yeşilaydın (2016) understand strategic innovation as an approach that arises from the interplay of innovative thinking and a company's long-term strategic orientation, offering a new value proposition to customers, stakeholders, and sometimes even entire industries. In this context, strategic innovation is not limited to the development of new products or processes, but represents a more comprehensive transformation that includes the reinterpretation of the business model, value creation methods, and rules of competition (Hancıoğlu & Yeşilaydın, 2016: 105–107).

The authors argue that strategic innovation enables companies to surprise their competitors, tap into new markets, and change the rules of the game in existing markets. In this way, companies can not only adapt to existing competitive conditions but also actively shape them. This transformative effect of strategic innovation requires a strategic link between both internal capabilities and external opportunities (Hancıoğlu & Yeşilaydın, 2016: 105–107).

Tankişi's (2018) study in the automotive sector emphasizes that innovation is a value directly linked to a company's vitality and its adaptability to environmental changes. The study shows that companies that successfully manage innovation and support this process through strategic leadership have significantly higher chances of survival and growth under competitive pressure. Conversely, companies that resist innovation lose strength over time because they cannot adapt to changing conditions (Tankişi, 2018: 41–42). In this sense, strategic leadership plays a crucial role, as it identifies innovation opportunities and aligns them with the company's strategic direction (Tankişi, 2018: 185).

Considering these findings together, it becomes clear that there is not only a supportive but also a mutually reinforcing synergy between strategic management and innovation. While strategic management establishes the appropriate direction, priorities, and resource allocation for innovation, innovation acts as a dynamic instrument that ensures the feasibility and sustainability of strategic decisions. The strategic innovation approach offers a holistic management style that strengthens a company's competitive position by integrating these two areas.

3.2. Innovation Strategies in Terms of Competitive Advantage

Globalization, technological progress, and the rapid integration of markets are intensifying competition between companies at both local and international levels. In this environment, traditional cost-cutting or differentiation strategies alone are no longer sufficient; they must be rethought from an innovative perspective. Hancıoğlu and Yeşilaydın (2016: 106–108) observe that in today's business world, innovation is not merely an "add-on activity" but rather one of the fundamental tools for achieving a sustainable competitive advantage. Innovation reduces costs, increases efficiency, productivity, and profitability, contributes to improved product and service quality, and facilitates market entry. The European Commission's 1995 strategy paper, the "Green Paper on Innovation," describes the role of

innovation for businesses and states. According to this document, innovation acts as a driving force for achieving long-term corporate goals, enables the emergence of new economic activities and sectors, and leads to the renewal of industrial structures. Innovation is at the heart of entrepreneurship. Innovation is understood not merely as an economic mechanism or a technical process, but as an instrument for solving societal problems (European Commission, 1995).

In this context, the decisive competitive advantage lies in the fact that innovation activities are not random experiments, but are carried out within the framework of innovation strategies that align with the company's overall direction. Satı and Işık (2011: 540) emphasize that the innovation strategy is a management framework that defines the fundamental steps and progress the company undertakes in the context of innovation. Depending on their innovation expectations, companies—analogue to defining their overall strategy—must develop an innovation strategy, taking into account their long-term goals, risk tolerance, market position, and technological orientation.

This strategy guides, on the one hand, the development of new products and services, the improvement of processes, and the redesign of business models; on the other hand, it requires adapting the organizational structure, culture, and human resources to the needs of these innovations. Satı and Işık (2011: 540) note that innovation has become a key element for economic growth, job creation, and quality of life. Therefore, they argue that the effectiveness of the innovation management process should be increased to improve the success of innovation efforts.

Kalay et al. (2015: 67–69) collected data from 132 managers in 66 companies in the TRB2 region to investigate the role of strategic innovation management in terms of competitive advantage and to analyze the key dimensions of innovation performance. The study examined the relationship between innovation performance and "strategic innovation management practices," which comprise components such as innovation strategy, organizational structure, innovation culture, technological capabilities, and customer-supplier relationships. The results show that innovation strategy and organizational structure, in particular, have a significant and positive impact on innovation performance; the effect of other dimensions, however, is less pronounced.

This finding highlights that innovation strategy, in terms of competitive advantage, is not merely a "technical" decision, but also a management decision that impacts the entire organization. Innovation efforts that are not clearly defined strategically and not aligned with the organizational structure struggle to focus on their objective. Conversely, a clear innovation strategy and a flexible organizational structure that supports this strategy facilitate the transformation of innovation into a competitive advantage. Tankişi (2018: 41–42) notes in his study that innovation is an effective tool for enhancing the competitiveness of companies and plays a crucial role in increasing profit, cash flow, and market share. The study observes that innovation is considered

a "powerful competitive weapon" in the literature, enabling companies to outperform their competitors in their respective industries. It is viewed as one of the fundamental ways to adapt to environmental changes and capitalize on new opportunities.

In conclusion, Kılıç's study (2023) highlights several key points for the strategic management of innovation processes. According to the study, it is necessary to expand resources for creating new products and jobs, shorten development and implementation cycles, rapidly integrate new technologies into the organizational structure, and foster a corporate climate in which innovations of all kinds can flourish. Furthermore, reducing development gaps in production and management processes, implementing innovation-oriented management to increase return on investment, and systematically identifying and eliminating barriers to innovation are considered crucial for securing competitive advantages. These findings underscore the importance of innovation strategies from a competitive advantage perspective. When innovation is placed at the heart of competitive positioning, it becomes a holistic strategic decision requiring the redesign of both internal business processes and relationships with the external environment.

3.3. The Relationship Between Strategic Management and Innovation in SMEs

One of the areas where the synergy between innovation and strategic management is particularly important in practice is small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). SMEs are known to represent the vast majority of businesses in Turkey and worldwide; however, the number of studies on strategic management and innovation in this sector is comparatively small. Çetinkaya and Gülbahar (2019: 349–350) state that SMEs constitute 99.8% of businesses in Turkey and form the backbone of the economy in terms of indicators such as employment, value added, and exports. Based on this fact, the authors investigated the relationship between strategic management and innovation in SMEs across various sectors in Ankara. The study sample comprised 300 SME managers from 35 sectors; data were collected via questionnaires and face-to-face interviews. Two separate scales were used in the analyses to measure perceptions of strategic management and innovation. The relationships between the scores achieved on these scales were statistically examined (Çetinkaya & Gülbahar, 2019: 350–355).

The results show that SME managers' perceptions of strategic management and innovation are at a moderate level; nevertheless, a significant and positive correlation exists between the two variables. Pearson correlation coefficients demonstrate a positive and moderate correlation between the total scores on the strategic management scale and the total scores on the innovation scale. Structural equation modeling also shows that an improved perception of strategic management is associated with an improved perception of innovation (Çetinkaya & Gülbahar, 2019: 355).

These results suggest that a better understanding of strategic management in SMEs directly and positively influences their innovative capacity. Strategic management practices such as setting long-term goals,

conducting environmental analyses, planning resource allocation, and aligning the organization with these goals promote the generation and implementation of innovative ideas. Conversely, strengthening innovation processes deepens the strategic perspectives of managers and increases companies' future-oriented decision-making capacity. The study by Kalay et al. (2015) in the TRB2 region also confirms the link between strategic innovation management and innovation performance in SMEs. The study found that strategic innovation management practices, such as innovation strategy and organizational structure, significantly increased the innovation performance of companies, mostly SMEs (Kalay et al., 2015: 67–69).

This finding supports the link between strategic management and innovation postulated by Çetinkaya and Gülbahar in the context of SMEs. The results of Tankişi (2018) also show a positive correlation between strategic leadership and innovation management processes in organizations similar to SMEs. It is emphasized that a management style that observes environmental trends, maintains open communication with employees, and is flexible and open to innovation is essential for the survival of the company, especially in industries with high competitive pressure and significant uncertainty (Tankişi, 2018: 134).

In summary, the relationship between strategic management and innovation in SMEs is characterized by a reciprocal and dynamic interaction. Strengthening strategic management approaches increases the innovative capacity of SMEs; conversely, developing innovation processes sharpens the strategic direction of these companies and thus strengthens their competitive position.

3.4. Strategic Innovation Management Practices and Innovation Performance

Strategic innovation management is based on an approach that understands the innovation process as a management domain encompassing all components of the organization and not limited solely to idea generation or R&D activities. In their model for explaining innovation performance, Kalay et al. (2015) examine strategic innovation management using five fundamental dimensions: innovation strategy, organizational structure, innovation culture, technological capabilities, and customer-supplier relationships. All of these dimensions were assessed as indicators of how innovation-friendly a company is and how intensively it promotes innovation (Kalay et al., 2015: 67–69).

Research also refers to the resource-based approach, which is prominent in the innovation literature. This approach posits that a company's unique and difficult-to-imitate resources, such as knowledge, experience, technology, and human capital, can be transformed into a competitive advantage through innovation. However, it is also emphasized that studies examining the relationship between innovation and business performance do not always yield consistent results. While some studies demonstrate the strong and positive impact of innovation on profitability and growth, others show that innovation investments do not always achieve the expected performance gains due to

cost pressures and uncertainty (Kalay et al., 2015: 67–69).

The results of the field study by Kalay and colleagues in the TRB2 region support this discussion with concrete data. The study found that the dimensions of innovation strategy and organizational structure positively and significantly influence innovation performance; in contrast, the effects of innovation culture, technological capabilities, and customer-supplier relationships were statistically weaker (Kalay et al., 2015: 69). This finding suggests that strategic alignment and organizational design are particularly important for improving innovation performance and that other dimensions should build upon this fundamental structure.

Satı and Işık (2011) view strategic innovation management not as a narrowly defined field focused solely on technology improvement, product development, or traditional cooperation networks, but as a process that compels a review of the company's entire business model. The authors argue that innovation must be "new to the company" and create economic value, and that the life cycles of companies change as soon as the innovative idea is implemented as a product, service, or business process (Satı & Işık, 2011: 540). The innovation strategy serves as a guideline for the organization, defining the areas in which it will innovate, the risks it will take, and the value proposition it will develop.

The authors emphasize that the effectiveness of innovation management must be increased to improve the success of innovation efforts. Rapid technological change is forcing companies to innovate more quickly, and innovation should therefore be considered a key element for economic growth, employment, and quality of life (Satı & Işık, 2011: 540). This emphasis demonstrates that strategic innovation management should consider not only short-term performance indicators but also the long-term sustainability of the company.

Tankişi's (2018) field study examines the performance dimension of strategic innovation management, particularly with regard to strategic leadership. The study notes that innovation is a "source of competitive advantage" for companies; however, poorly managed innovation processes can lead to adaptation problems and wasted resources. Participant statements indicate that practices such as a flexible organizational structure, an employee-centric management approach, continuous learning, and close monitoring of developments in the environment strengthen the innovation process (Tankişi, 2018: 41–42, 185).

Tankişi's (2018) field study examines the performance dimension of strategic innovation management, particularly with regard to strategic leadership. These practices illustrate that strategic innovation management should be considered not only in terms of structure, but also with regard to cultural and leadership dimensions. The study by Çetinkaya and Gülbahar (2019) on SMEs indirectly supports the link between strategic innovation management and innovation performance. The positive and moderate correlation between strategic management and innovation perception shows that developing strategic perspectives among managers also strengthens innovation processes (Çetinkaya & Gülba-

har, 2019: 355). This suggests that the success of strategic innovation management practices is closely linked to formal structures and processes, but also to the mindset and perceptions of managers.

In summary, the relationship between strategic innovation management practices and innovation performance is multidimensional and conditional. While structural elements such as innovation strategy and organizational structure have a direct and strong impact on performance, elements such as corporate culture, leadership style, relationships with external stakeholders, and technological infrastructure play a supporting role within this basic structure. The literature shows that the innovation performance of companies, and thus their competitive advantages, are strengthened when the synergy between strategic management and innovation is properly structured, innovation is addressed at a strategic level, and it is supported by management.

4. Organizational Dimensions of the Relationship Between Strategic Management and Innovation

4.1. Strategic Leadership and Innovation Management

The link between strategic management and innovation is most evident in a company's top management and its leadership style. Finkelstein and Hambrick (2009) define strategic leaders as members of top management who play a crucial role in the company's long-term success, analyze the external environment, make key decisions, and are responsible for their implementation. According to Rowe (2001), a strategic leader is someone who can balance short-term financial performance with long-term competitive advantage while simultaneously formulating the company's vision. Elenkov (2005) connects strategic leadership with the company's ability to identify opportunities and threats in the environment, develop appropriate strategies, and align employees with these strategies.

Papadakis and Bourantas (1998) and Sosik et al. (2005) emphasize that the leader is the individual who shapes the company's culture and decision-making processes. In this context, the strategic leader is viewed not only as a decision-maker but also as an actor who holistically shapes the company's strategic direction, organizational structure, and innovative capacity. Tankişi's study of car dealerships shows that strategic leadership processes and innovation management practices are closely linked and that there is a positive correlation between the two (Tankişi, 2018: 3). According to the study, innovation management processes function more consistently in organizations with leaders who systematically analyze the environment, share the vision with employees, manage change, and take risks. This facilitates the creation, testing, and commercialization of new ideas (Tankişi, 2018: 3–4).

The crucial role of strategic leadership is closely linked to the quality of the tasks performed by the leader. Elenkov (2005) emphasizes that innovation is closely connected to the impact of leadership on organizational culture, organizational climate, and organizational learning. Barutçugil (2014) defines the strategic leader as the person who establishes and invests in the organization's core competencies, aligns employees toward common goals, and manages change processes.

From this perspective, the contribution of strategic leadership to innovation management lies in creating a climate in which creative ideas can emerge, lessons can be learned from mistakes, and organizational learning processes can be supported (Tankişi, 2018: 16–17).

Tankişi's (2018) findings highlight the influence of strategic leadership practices on the innovation management process, particularly in the dimensions of vision, communication, and change management. The car dealership managers participating in the study reported that applying strategic leadership principles led to faster innovation-related decisions, aligned resource allocation with these decisions, and increased employee willingness to participate in innovation initiatives (Tankişi, 2018: 26–27). As Yalçın and Ay (2007) also emphasized, innovative projects become concrete business outcomes, rather than remaining an abstract ideal, to the extent that strategic leaders can translate the company vision into employees' daily activities.

The literature on innovation management shows that the strategic leader in this phase acts not only as a visionary but also as a systems designer, creating and managing innovation processes. Satı and Işık (2011) define innovation management as a set of management activities that link technology, business processes, and interpersonal relationships in such a way as to foster innovation and manage innovation activities within a specific process. This definition clarifies the role of the strategic leader: they transform the company's vision into an innovation strategy, design the structures and processes appropriate for this strategy, and foster an organizational culture that enables innovation (Kılıç, 2023: 86–87).

The findings of Kalay et al. (2015) in their study of companies in the TRB2 region confirm this picture. The study revealed that innovation strategy and organizational structure positively influence innovation performance. Innovation culture, technological competence, and customer/supplier relationships showed no significant influence in the sample studied (Kalay et al., 2015: 68–69). This finding highlights the connection between strategic leadership and innovation management, particularly through the clarity of the strategy and the structural conditions. In other words, the ability of top management to define a strategy that clearly prioritizes innovation and to establish an organizational structure that supports this strategy directly impacts innovation performance (Kalay et al., 2015: 72–73).

In this context, strategic leadership becomes a key variable for formulating the innovation strategy, aligning resources with this strategy, and integrating employees into the innovation goals. The relationship between strategic management and innovation management is strengthened by the ability of leaders to analyze the environment, assess risks, and seize opportunities in a timely manner, and their ability to align internal structure and human resources with these opportunities (Tankişi, 2018: 29–30; Kılıç, 2023: 86–87).

4.2. Strategic Human Resources Management and Service Innovation

The sustainability of innovation at the organizational level largely depends on how human resources are managed. As Özsungur (2017) emphasizes in her

service innovation-focused strategic human resources management model, strategic human resources management aims to build a bridge between the vision and mission of the business and its human resources practices. In this approach, human resources decisions are not seen merely as technical processes aimed at meeting short-term personnel needs, but as long-term investments supporting the organization's competitive strategy (Özsungur, 2017: 11–12).

Strategic human resources management positions human resources as a "strategic value" rather than a "cost element". As Bingöl (2014) also points out, attracting, retaining, developing, and monitoring the performance of qualified employees, when considered together with the strategic management process, constitutes sustainable competitive advantage. In Özsungur's model, this understanding is based on the assumption that human resources functions – recruitment, training and development, performance evaluation, career planning, and reward – should be designed in a way that is compatible with the innovation strategy. Thus, the organization aims to create a human resource profile that is open to innovation, ready for change, and focused on learning (Özsungur, 2017: 12).

Tankişi (2018: 29–30) also considers human resources as one of the key areas of competitive advantage for the business within the context of strategic leadership. The research emphasizes that human capital, consisting of elements such as knowledge, skills, experience, and motivation, directly affects the adaptability, flexibility, and innovation power of the business, especially in a rapidly changing technological environment. Finkelstein and Hambrick (2009) state that businesses competing in dynamic environments differentiate themselves not only with their physical assets or financial resources, but also with their human resources, which determine how they use these resources. In this framework, strategic human resources management serves as a framework that manages human capital in a way that is consistent with innovation goals.

Since innovation in the service sector is often shaped directly through employee-customer interaction, strategic human resources management is at the center of service innovation. Özsungur (2017) states that service innovation; It is stated that this is closely related to the capacity of employees to rethink service processes, transform customer feedback into creative solutions, and improve the service experience (Özsungur, 2017: 14). Baker and Sinkula (2009) and Storey and Kelly (2001) also show that the learning, knowledge sharing, and creativity levels of human resources are decisive in the success of service innovation (cited in Özsungur, 2017: 14–15). Therefore, an innovation-oriented human resources system should consider creativity and willingness to learn in the recruitment process; improve employees' problem-solving and customer-oriented thinking skills through training programs; and particularly encourage innovative behaviors in performance evaluation and reward mechanisms (Özsungur, 2017: 14–15).

In Özsungur's model, two important psychosocial elements supporting service innovation stand out: ethical leadership and psychological capital. Brown et al.

(2005) define ethical leadership as; While defining ethical leadership as a form of leadership that reflects values such as justice, honesty, reliability, and respect for employees in its behavior, Dhar (2016) revealed that ethical leadership positively influences employees' innovative behaviors both in and out of their roles. Accordingly, ethical leadership strengthens employees' trust in the organization and management, increasing their willingness to take risks and try new things; thus, it prepares the necessary psychological ground for service innovation (Özsungur, 2017: 15).

Psychological capital is a concept consisting of self-efficacy, hope, optimism, and resilience dimensions, expressing employees' capacity to withstand difficulties, try new approaches, and focus on goals (Bandura, 1997). Kim et al. (2016) and Bouckennooghe et al. (2015) show that employees with high psychological capital are more willing to engage in innovative behaviors, learn from mistakes, and actively participate in organizational change processes. In light of these findings, Özsungur (2017: 16–17) argues that strategic human resources management, which promotes service innovation, should be supported not only through technical skills and formal qualifications but also through practices aimed at strengthening employees' psychological capital. In conclusion, strategic human resources management represents the "human dimension" of the relationship with innovation; it directly contributes to service innovation through ethical leadership, psychological capital, and innovation-oriented HR policies. When strategic leadership and strategic HR management are considered together, a holistic management framework emerges that supports organizations' innovation capacity (Tankişi, 2018: 29–30; Özsungur, 2017: 11–17).

4.3. Organizational Structure, Organizational Culture, and Technological Competence

The relationship between strategic management and innovation is not limited solely to leadership and human resources; the structural characteristics of the organization, its cultural climate, and technological capabilities are also among the fundamental elements determining this relationship. Satı and Işık (2011) define innovation management as the firm's management of technology, business processes, and human relations in a way that supports and encourages innovation, and link innovation success to the resources available and the ability to manage these resources. Kalay et al. (2015), within this framework, consider innovation strategy, organizational structure, innovation culture, technological capability, and customer-supplier relations as the fundamental dimensions affecting firm innovation performance (Kalay et al., 2015: 68–69).

In the study conducted by Kalay et al. (2015: 72–73) on businesses in the TRB2 region, it was concluded that innovation strategy and organizational structure significantly and positively affect innovation performance; while innovation culture, technological capability, and customer and supplier relations did not have a direct effect within the sample. This finding indicates that, in order to support innovation at the organizational level, strategic orientation and structural arrangements must first be clarified. From a strategic management

perspective, the innovation strategy provides a framework that determines in which areas, with which resources, and with which collaboration models the business will innovate; the organizational structure, on the other hand, shapes the network of relationships and decision-making mechanisms through which this strategy will be implemented (Kalay et al., 2015: 73–75).

Hancıoğlu and Yeşilaydın (2016: 105–106), addressing the concept of strategic innovation within the context of strategic management, draw attention to the synergy between innovative thinking and corporate strategies. The authors define strategic innovation as an approach that integrates strategy and innovation, aimed at creating new value for customers, catching competitors off guard, expanding the market, and creating new markets. According to Markides (1997), strategic innovation is a way of thinking that questions the established rules of competition in the sector, redefines what the customer "values," and combines these new value propositions with new business models. Sniukas (2007) also views strategic innovation as an effort to create differentiated value propositions for customers and stakeholders by going beyond the existing strategic position (cited in Hancıoğlu & Yeşilaydın, 2016: 109).

Hancıoğlu and Yeşilaydın (2016: 109) emphasize that strategic innovation is shaped around four fundamental elements at the organizational level: culture, processes, people, and resources. In organizations that embrace strategic innovation, the culture has a character that encourages risk-taking, is open to learning from mistakes, and supports creativity and flexibility. Processes have a systematic and repeatable structure for generating, evaluating, and implementing new ideas; innovative projects are managed within a specific method, rather than being random initiatives (Hancıoğlu & Yeşilaydın, 2016: 109–110). In terms of the human dimension, collaborative teams where employees from different disciplines work together, cross-functional projects, and strong communication channels come to the forefront. The resource dimension refers to the allocation of financial assets, technological infrastructure, and information resources in a manner consistent with strategic innovation goals, and securing the time and budget allocated to innovative projects (Hancıoğlu & Yeşilaydın, 2016: 110–111).

These elements concretize the relationship between strategic management and innovation management through organizational structure and culture. A flexible structure that strengthens horizontal relationships and reduces bureaucratic obstacles facilitates the circulation of new ideas, the flow of information between different departments, and rapid decision-making. Conversely, in overly hierarchical, rigid, and risk-averse structures, innovative ideas often get lost in the decision-making chain or are not sufficiently embraced (Kalay et al., 2015: 73–75; Hancıoğlu & Yeşilaydın, 2016: 109–110).

Technological competence is another decisive dimension in this relationship. Kalay et al. (2015: 68–69) define innovation management as the firm's ability to integrate technology, business processes, and human relations in a way that supports innovation; while they associate technological competence with the business's

capacity to monitor, select, adapt, and effectively use new technologies within the organization. Businesses with high technological competence can follow market and industry developments more closely, direct R&D and design activities according to strategic goals, and transform innovations in areas such as digitalization and automation into a competitive advantage. Conversely, weak technological competence can lead to innovation strategies remaining on paper and weaken the organization's long-term competitiveness (Kalay et al., 2015: 72–73).

To summarize the organizational dimensions of the strategic management-innovation relationship; strategic leadership, strategic human resources management, organizational structure, culture, and technological competence form complementary links. Leadership; While leadership represents the vision, strategy, and will to change, human resources organizes the human capital that will carry and sustain this vision. Organizational structure and culture show how innovation will be reflected in daily operations, through what mechanisms decisions will be made, and what kinds of behaviors employees will be rewarded. Technological competence, on the other hand, determines how all these efforts will be supported with concrete tools. Therefore, the relationship between strategic management and innovation is too multi-dimensional and dynamic to be reduced to a single variable. It has been observed that the synergy between strategic management and innovation is stronger in organizations where supportive practices in the areas of leadership, human resources, structure, culture, and technology are carried out together; conversely, when one of these elements is weak, the innovation capacity remains limited (Tankişi, 2018: 29–30; Özsungur, 2017: 11–17; Kalay et al., 2015: 68–75; Hancıoğlu & Yeşilaydın, 2016: 105–111). Therefore, it is critically important for businesses to rethink their strategic management approaches within a framework that holistically considers the organizational dimensions of innovation, in order to ensure the sustainability of their competitive advantage.

5. RESULT AND EVALUATION

This study reveals that strategic management and innovation are not two separate fields, but rather different sides of the same picture. Strategic management establishes the framework that determines where the business wants to go and what steps it will take along the way; innovation becomes one of the fundamental tools that fills this framework and ensures the business's survival in the competitive arena. Especially in an environment of high uncertainty, fierce competition, and rapid technological change, it is clear that simply planning or simply pursuing innovation is insufficient; these two perspectives must be structured together, mutually reinforcing each other. Studies show that innovation is not a process that can be left to chance or reduced to mere "creative ideas"; rather, it is a management area that gains meaning when integrated with strategy. It is understood that in businesses where the innovation strategy is not clearly defined, the organizational structure is not arranged to support this strategy, and resource allocation is not made accordingly, well-inten-

tioned innovation efforts do not yield the desired results. Conversely, it can be said that businesses that clarify their innovation strategy, establish a flexible and learning-oriented organizational structure, and take ownership of this process at the top management level significantly increase their innovation performance and competitiveness. From the perspective of SMEs, the situation becomes even more critical. Despite being one of the pillars of the economy, these businesses operate with limited resources, making it essential for them to develop both strategic thinking and innovation skills to survive and grow. Findings show that increased awareness of strategic management in SMEs positively impacts their perception and application of innovation, indicating a bidirectional relationship between the two areas. Therefore, it is crucial for SMEs to clarify their medium- and long-term goals without getting lost in the pressure of daily operations; and to create a realistic yet innovative roadmap to achieve these goals. At the organizational level, several critical links complete the picture: strategic leadership, human resources management, organizational structure, culture, and technological competence. Strategic leadership requires an approach that can read the opportunities and risks in the environment, transform this reading into a clear vision, and unite employees around this vision. Human resources stands out as the party that selects, develops, and retains human capital that will carry this vision and is open to learning and innovation. Organizational structure and culture require an environment where innovative ideas can emerge and be discussed, where mistakes are not punished, and where trial and error are seen as a natural part of the learning process. Technological competence, on the other hand, represents the infrastructure that enables all these efforts to be supported by tangible tools. The weakness of any of these links significantly limits the potential of the strategic management-innovation relationship. Generally speaking, the strategic innovation approach offers a broader framework that goes beyond the traditional "simply renewing the product" mentality, requiring a holistic approach that considers the business model, value proposition, market positioning, and organizational structure together. The ability of businesses to transform themselves from actors merely adapting to existing competitive conditions into actors actively transforming these conditions is closely related to the extent to which this approach is internalized. Therefore, whether in large-scale enterprises or SMEs, establishing a management approach that explicitly includes the innovation dimension in strategic planning processes and places innovation projects at the center of the strategic agenda seems inevitable for organizations that want to survive and differentiate themselves in the coming period. In conclusion, this study demonstrates that strategic management and innovation should not be viewed as two separate, juxtaposed concepts, but rather as two fundamental management areas that complement each other and only gain meaning when considered together. The key to long-term success lies not in establishing a purely theoretical connection between these two areas, but in achieving holistic alignment that extends from goals and organizational structure to leadership style, human

resource policies, and technology choices. Businesses that achieve this alignment are more likely to adapt more quickly to changing competitive conditions, identify new opportunities more readily, and transform innovation into a sustainable competitive advantage.

References

1. Abraham, J.L., & Knight, D.J. (2001). Strategic innovation. *Strategy and Leadership*, 29(1), 21-27.
2. Aktan, C.C. (2008), *Stratejik Yönetim ve Stratejik Planlama*, Çimento İşveren Dergisi, 22(4), 4-21.
3. Aslan, İ. (2019). İşletme yönetiminde stratejik rekabet üstünlüğünün sağlanmasında; bir aracı olarak inovasyon stratejilerinin önemi. *International Journal of Social and Humanities Sciences Research (JSHSR)*, 6(32), 9-21.
4. Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
5. Barutçugil, İ. (2014). *Liderlik* (1. Basım). İstanbul: Kariyer Yayınları.
6. Bingöl, D. (2014). *İnsan Kaynakları Yönetimi*, Beta.
7. Bircan, İ. (2003); *Kamuda Stratejik Yönetim ve AB Politikaları: Kamu Yönetiminde Kalite*, 3. Ulusal Kongresi Bildirileri, TODAİE Yayın No: 319, Ankara: TODAİE Yayınları.
8. Bouckennooghe, D., Zafar, A., Raja, U. (2015). How Ethical Leadership Shapes Employees' Job Performance: The Mediating Roles of Goal Congruence and Psychological Capital, *J Bus Ethics*, 129: 251–264.
9. Brown, M. E., Treviño, L. K., Harrison, D. A. (2005). Ethical leadership: a social learning perspective for construct development and testing. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 97 (2): 117-134.
10. Cormican, K. & O'sullıvan, D. (2004). *Auditing Best Practice for Effective Product Innovation Management, Technovation*.
11. Çetinkaya, F. F. ve Gülbahar, O. (2019). Stratejik yönetim ve inovasyon ilişkisi: KOBİ'ler üzerine bir araştırma. *Ahi Evran Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 5(2), 349-367.
12. Damanpour, Fariborz (1991); "Organizational Innovation: A Meta Analysis Of Effects Of Determinants And Moderators", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 34, 555-90.
13. Dhar, R. L. (2016). Ethical leadership and its impact on service innovative behavior: The role of LMX and job autonomy, *57*, 139-148.
14. Diken, A., Öge, S., Aslan, Ş., Aktan C. C. (2006); *Geleceği Kazanmanın Yolu: Stratejik Yönetim*, 14. Ulusal Yönetim ve Organizasyon Kongresi Bildiriler Kitabı, Erzurum.
15. Drejer, A. (2006). Strategic innovation: A new perspective on strategic management. *Handbook of Business Strategy*, 7(1), 143-147.
16. Drucker, P. (1985). *The discipline of innovation*. Harvard Business Review, 1-9.
17. Elenkov, D.S., Judge, W. ve Wright, P. (2005). Strategic Leadership and Executive Innovation Influence: An International Multi-Cluster Comparative Study. *Strategic Management Journal*, (26), 665–682.
18. European Commission (1995). *Green paper on innovation*. Erişim Tarihi: 05.12.2025, http://europa.eu/documents/comm/green_papers/pdf/com95_688_en.pdf.
19. Finkelstein, S. ve Hambrick, D. C. (2009). *Strategic Leadership: Theory and Research on Executives, Top Management Teams and Boards*. Oxford University Press Finalist, Academy of Management.
20. Govindarajan, V., & Trimble, C. (2004). Strategic innovation and the science of learning. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 45(2), 67-75.
21. Hamel, G. (1998). Strategy innovation and the quest for value. *Sloan Management Review*, 39(2), 7-14.
22. Hancıoğlu, Y., & Yeşilaydın, G. (2016). Stratejik yönetimde yeni bir rekabet yaklaşımı: Stratejik inovasyon. *Uluslararası Yönetim İktisat ve İşletme Dergisi*, 12(29), 105-124.
23. Kalay, F., Tuncer, C. O., Kızıldere, C., & Kalay, H. A. (2016). Stratejik inovasyon yönetimi uygulamalarının firma inovasyon performansı üzerindeki etkileri. *Bilgi Ekonomisi ve Yönetimi Dergisi*, 10(2).
24. Kılıç, C. (2023). Stratejik yönetim ve inovasyon. İçinde V. Batdı & S. Ayaz (Ed.), *İnovasyon yönetimi ve inovatif metaverse devrimi* (ss. 69–90). Anı Yayıncılık.
25. Kim, T. T., Karatepe, O. M., Lee, G. (2017). Psychological contract breach and service innovation behavior: psychological capital as a mediator, *Serv Bus*, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11628-017-0347-4>.
26. Markides, C. (1997). Strategic innovation. *Sloan Management Review*, Spring, 9-23.
27. Morris, L. (2013). Three dimensions of innovation. *International Management Review*, 9(2), 5-10.
28. OECD ve Eurostat (2005). *Yenilik Verilerinin Toplanması ve Yorumlanması İçin İlkeler* (3. Basım), TÜBİTAK.
29. Özgür Güler, E., & Kanber, S. (2011). İnovasyon aktivitelerinin inovasyon performansı üzerine etkileri: İmalat sanayii uygulaması. *Çukurova Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 20(1), 61-76.
30. Özsungur, F. (2017). Hizmet inovasyonu odaklı stratejik insan kaynakları yönetimi. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Management Inquiries*, 1(1), 8-18.
31. Papadakis, V. ve Bourantas, D. (1998). The Chief Executive Officer As Corporate Champion of Technological Innovation: An Empirical Investigation. *Technology Analysis and Strategic Management*, 10 (1), 89–110.
32. Rogers, Everett, M. (1995); *Diffusion of Innovation*, 4th.ed., N.Y.: The Free Press.
33. Rowe, W.G. (2001). *Creating Wealth In Organisations: The Role of Strategic Leadership*. *Academy of Management Executive*, 15 (1), 81–94.
34. Satı, Z. E., & Işık, Ö. G. D. Ö. (2011). İnovasyon ve stratejik yönetim sinerjisi: Stratejik inovasyon. *Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 9(2), 538-559.

35. Sattler, M. (2011). Excellence in Innovation Management: A Meta-Analytic Review on the Predictors of Innovation Performance. (1. Basım). Germany: Gabler Verlag.
36. Schlegelmilch, B. B., Diamantopoulos, A., & Kreuz, P. (2003). Strategic innovation: The construct, its drivers and its strategic outcomes. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 11, 117-132.
37. Sosik, J.J., Berson, Y., Jung, I. D., ve Jaussi, K.S. (2005). The Strategic Leadership of Top Executives In High-Tech Organisations. *Organisational Dynamics*, 34 (1), 47-61.
38. Tankişi, B. (2018). Stratejik liderlik ile inovasyon yönetimi arasındaki ilişki: Otomotiv bayileri üzerine nitel bir araştırma. Yüksek Lisans Tezi Düzce Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Toplam Kalite Yönetimi Ana Bilim Dalı.
39. Trott, Paul (1998); "Innovation Management & New Product Development" Financial Times Pitman Publishing.
40. Uzkuurt, C. (2010). İnovasyon Yönetimi: İnovasyon Nedir, Nasıl Yapılır ve Nasıl Pazarlanır? Ankara Sanayi Odası Yayını , Ankara.
41. Ünal, A. ve Kılınç, İ. (2016). İnovasyon yönetimi. (Editör: Kahraman Çatı). Girişimcilik ve İnovasyon Yönetimi. Ankara: Nobel Akademik Yayıncılık, 99-134.
42. Yalçın, B. ve Ay, C. (2007). Bilgi Toplumunda Örgütsel Dönüşüm Açısından Stratejik Mimari Boyutunda Stratejik Liderlik Analizi, (12. Bölüm). Toplam Kalite ve Stratejik Yönetimde Yeni Eğilimler (1. Basım). Ankara: Gazi Kitabevi.